

Additional File 11: Fully adjusted Odds Ratios (and 95%-CIs) of access to healthcare comparing between access models used in the first 15 months (ref=HV), with urban/rural

Legend: HV=Health care voucher; EHC=electronic health card; x-axis with 95% confidence intervals on a log-scale